

Thematic Piece: Food Security and Climate Change

Joint Programming Initiative
on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change
FACCEJPI.NET

This series of thematic pieces spotlights FACCE-JPI projects on a specific theme. This piece will centre on projects with the theme of food security and climate change.

What is food security and how is it affected by climate change?

Food security is generally defined as existing “when **all people**, at **all times**, have physical and economic **access** to sufficient, **safe** and **nutritious** food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life”.

Food security is affected by climate change through increasing temperatures, changing precipitation patterns and greater frequency of extreme events. Future food production will have to deal with high temperatures, dryness, increased salinity, damage from extreme events and disruption in supply chains. Therefore, mitigation of emissions from agriculture and adaptation to climate change will be needed.

[An integrated approach to the challenge of sustainable food systems: adaptive and mitigatory strategies to address climate change and malnutrition \(SYSTEMIC\)](#)

Knowledge Hub on Food and Nutrition Security call

Duration: July 1, 2020 - June 30, 2024

Short description of the project

The SYSTEMIC project aims to implement adaptive strategies for sustainable food production, consumption and public health by addressing the various impacts of climate change on nutrition quality and food composition and defining standards to achieve food and nutrition security.

Key insights related to food security and climate change:

- The current state of knowledge about climate and climate change effects on the biophysical environment of food and nutrition systems is essential;
- Resource productivity and efficiency can be affected by socio-economic factors;
- **Meal plans** can be optimised to reduce environmental impact and ensure adequate nutritional intake, affordable prices and cultural acceptability;
- Modelling can be a useful tool to optimise meal plans and analyse their costs and impacts on the environment

Major publications

Benvenuti, Luca, Alberto De Santis, and Paola Cacchione. "Multi-indicator design and assessment of sustainable diet plans." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 313 (2021): 127699. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127699>

Dibari, Camilla, and al. "Climate change impacts on the Alpine, Continental and Mediterranean grassland systems of Italy: A review." *Italian Journal of Agronomy* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.4081/ija.2021.1843>

Benvenuti, Luca, and Alberto De Santis. "Making a sustainable diet acceptable: an emerging programming model with applications to schools and nursing homes menus." *Frontiers in Nutrition* 7 (2020): 562833. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2020.562833>

Delivering food security on limited land (DEVIL)

FACCE-JPI /Belmont Forum

Duration: February 1, 2015 — January 31, 2018

Short description of the project

DEVIL envisions solutions to feed a growing population with limited land resources by examining feedbacks and interactions between land-use change and food security dynamics.

This project aims to propose an integrated modelling system that will examine a range of scenarios, including production-side and demand-side measures to improve food security, as well as the global feedbacks of these scenarios on land use, food supply and the differential impacts in three regions: South America, Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia.

Key insights related to food security and climate change

- Projected population and food demand increases would require more land and have disastrous consequences on global climate change, biodiversity and other environmental aspects;
- **Sustainable intensification** could limit the adverse impacts of projected population increases and dietary transitions, but they would not be eliminated;
- **Reduction in overconsumption of livestock products and reduced pre-and post-consumer food waste** is necessary to deliver nutrition security in a globally sustainable manner.

Major publications

Molotoks, Amy, et al. "Comparing the impact of future cropland expansion on global biodiversity and carbon storage across models and scenarios." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B* 375.1794 (2020): 20190189. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0189>

Balmford, Andrew, et al. "The environmental costs and benefits of high-yield farming." *Nature Sustainability* 1.9 (2018): 477-485. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0138-5>

Smith, Pete, et al. "Impacts on terrestrial biodiversity of moving from a 2°C to a 1.5°C target." *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A* 376 (2018): 20160456 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0456>

AFGROLAND

FACCE-JPI/Belmont Forum

Duration: March 1, 2015 — September 30, 2018

Short description of the project

Global agro-food-energy system changes impact African countries, particularly regarding sustainable

land management, agricultural production, food security, socio-economic outcomes, pressure on land and natural resources, and governance. This project aims to identify drivers of change within global agro-food-energy systems, and how they impact on and are impacted by governance changes at regional, national, and local levels.

Key insights related to food security and climate change

- Large Agricultural Investments (LAIs) **shifted smallholder farms to commercial agriculture**, leading to socioeconomic, food security and environmental changes in Kenya, Madagascar, and Mozambique;
- LAIs contributed to deforestation in Mozambique, and water shortage and pollution in Kenya;
- Impacts of LAIs on food security varied. Engaged households in LAIs were more food secure compared to non-engaged households;
- Commercial agriculture can be a component in **sustainable development strategies** under certain conditions (i.e., business models and governance).

Major publications

Oberlack, Christoph, et al. "Why do large-scale agricultural investments induce different socio-economic, food security, and environmental impacts? Evidence from Kenya, Madagascar, and Mozambique" *Ecology and Society* 16.4 (2021): 18. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12653-260418>

Zaehring, Julie G et al. "Large-scale agricultural investments in Eastern Africa: consequences for small-scale farmers and the environment" *Ecosystem and People* 17.1 (2021): 342-357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2021.1939789>

Fitawek, Wegayehu and Sheryl L Hendriks, "Evaluating the Impact of Large-Scale Agricultural Investments on Household Food Security Using an Endogenous Switching Regression Model" *Land* 10.3 (2021): 323. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land10030323>

For an overview of all FACCE-JPI projects, check the [project wheel](#) which gathers information on the 153 projects funded by FACCE-JPI. Both past and currently running projects are included.

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